

ON THE CHEMISTRY OF "6257"—A SULPHA COMPOUND
ACTIVE AGAINST *V. CHOLERAE*

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A structure* for the "sulfa compound" obtained by the interaction of 2 molecules of sulphathiazole with 3 molecules of formaldehyde, has been suggested.

The recent observations on the chemistry of sulphathiazole show that the high *in vitro* activity of this sulphanilamide derivative may even be maintained in *in vivo* by reacting it with succinic or phthalic anhydride (cf. Poth and Ross, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1944, 29, 785), or, with formalin (Bhatnagar *et al.*, *Nature*, 1948, 161, 395). The latter reaction has yielded a product with an empirical formula $C_{21}H_{22}O_6N_6S_4$ the constitution of which has not yet been ascribed (cf. Bhatnagar, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1948, i, 719). In a recent note Basu (*Science & Culture*, 1948, 14, 36) has suggested that the compound may possess the structure (I). In the present paper certain other characteristics of the compound and the mode of behaviour of sulphathiazole with formalin have been further elucidated. It may be recorded here that the above compound (I) is obtained even when sulphathiazole is treated with hexamine in place of a formalin solution. The condensation with formalin may be brought about by mixing an alcoholic solution, acid solution, or alkaline solution of sulphathiazole with formalin. In the latter case the reaction mixture is to be acidified in order to isolate the condensation product $C_{21}H_{22}O_6N_6S_4$ (I).

The compound itself is insoluble in alkali but on warming it goes into solution, which when warmed with a solution of silver nitrate forms beautiful silver mirror. It is also insoluble in ammonia, but on warming it goes into solution which when saturated with carbon dioxide afforded a solid melting at 110° . This is easily soluble in dilute alkali and remains undissolved in dilute acid. On warming the above alkali solution, however, with silver nitrate, silver mirror is obtained, as is with the parent compound. The ammonia solution itself on treatment with silver nitrate affords a white, comparatively stable silver salt containing 27.8% of silver indicating that the compound (I) has undergone a fission to afford a product (II) of the formula $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N_3S_2$. If the filtrate after the separation of the solid of m. p. 110° be acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, a gummy mass is obtained. This also reduces a silver nitrate solution forming mirror when warmed with alkali. But the mother-liquor (filtrate after separation of the gummy mass) by diazo reaction indicates the presence of free primary aromatic amine. The compound (I) itself when heated with dilute alkali (5% caustic soda) affords pure sulphathiazole.

* After the paper has been communicated it came to the notice of the author that Druey (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, 31, 179) has described the preparation of the compound and has suggested two formulae for the same. According to the investigation as carried out in the course of this work and as shown in a subsequent paper (Basu, *this issue*, p. 130) it appears that the properties and characteristics of the compound are best satisfied by the formulae as advocated in the body of this paper"

The reasons for which the structure (I) is being ascribed to the compound are :—

(a) It readily evolves formaldehyde when warmed with alkali, as is evident by the reduction of silver nitrate.

(b) It also evolves formaldehyde when digested with dilute sulphuric acid, as is evident by the reduction of a dichromate solution. In this connection it should be mentioned that hexamine on treatment with alkali does not evolve formaldehyde but on digesting with acid it is decomposed to formaldehyde and ammonia.

(c) It is also formed when sulphathiazole is heated under reflux in alcoholic solution with hexamine. Ammonia vapour escapes during the reaction.

(d) It is insoluble in dilute acid ; it does not react with bromine or sodium bisulphite solution.

(e) It is hydrolysable to its parent product, sulphathiazole, by alkali.

(f) N¹-Methyl derivative of sulphathiazole reacts with formalin but the resulting condensation product is insoluble both in dilute acid and alkali on warming.

(g) The N⁴-acetylsulphathiazole does not react with formalin.

(h) Sulphathiazole reacts with formic acid to afford a different product, N⁴-formylsulphathiazole (III), which is soluble in dilute acid and reduces silver nitrate to mirror when heated with a solution of silver nitrate in presence of alkali.

As sulphathiazole itself may exist in two isomeric forms (IV) and (V) (cf. Shepherd, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2532), so the formalin condensation product, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_6\text{S}_4$, may also exist in isomeric forms where the methylene group, as marked with asterisk in (I), may be linked either to N¹-atom, or to the thiazole ring N, as shown by the dotted lines in the figure

The characteristic, as shown under (a), tends to indicate the presence of methylal group in the molecule, and that under (b) supports the methylene linkage in structure (I), as similarly found in that of hexamine.

The non-solubility of the compound indicates that the compound is methylene-3: 3'-bis-(4-hydroxymethyl-2-sulphanilimido-2:3-dihydrothiazole).

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of Formalin with Sulphathiazole

Preparation of "6257".—Sulphathiazole (5.1 g.) was dissolved in 200 c.c. of dilute alcohol (80%) by warming and the solution was filtered off. To the clear filtrate 3 c.c. of formalin (36% formaldehyde), dissolved in 7 c.c. of alcohol, were added with stirring. The mixture was left aside when the compound slowly separated out in crops of needles, m. p. 276-78°, yield 5.2 g. (Found: N, 13.65. $C_{21}H_{22}O_4N_6S_4$ requires N, 14.43 per cent).

The same compound was obtained when formalin was added to a dilute hydrochloric acid solution of sulphathiazole. On treating the alkali solution of sulphathiazole with formalin no solid separated out; but the reaction mixture on acidification afforded the identical product.

Sulphathiazole (5.1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (80%), filtered and the solution was refluxed with pure hexamine (1 g.) for 5 hours. During heating ammonia vapour was found to escape. The reaction mixture was left overnight. Next day the crystals formed (4.8 g.) were collected and found to melt at 276°, not depressing when mixed with the product obtained by condensing sulphathiazole with formalin. The mother-liquor on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid afforded another crop (1.0 g.), m. p. 274-76°. The total yield was almost theoretical. The product is insoluble in almost all common organic solvents. (Found: N, 14.22. $C_{21}H_{22}O_4N_6S_4$ requires N, 14.43 per cent).

Characteristics.—The compound is insoluble in dilute acid and in dilute alkali. On boiling the acid suspension a pink colour developed, and on warming the alkali suspension the compound underwent dissolution. On acidification a solid was isolated which melted indifferently at 268° with decomposition. The alkali solution on warming with silver nitrate produced a beautiful silver mirror. The compound does not react with bromine, nor with sodium bisulphite solution.

Hydrolysis to Sulphathiazole.—The compound (1, 2 g.) was refluxed for 3½ hours with 50 c.c. of caustic soda solution (5%). The solution was filtered, cooled and acidified to Congo red. Crystals separating (1.7 g.) were collected and recrystallised from alcohol (95%) when sulphathiazole, separated out, m. p. 202°. The melting point was not depressed when mixed with an authentic sample of sulphathiazole. (Found: N, 16.40. $C_9H_9O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 16.67 per cent).

Treatment with Ammonia.—The compound was insoluble in ammonia, but on warming on a water-bath it gradually went into solution. A part of this solution was cooled, saturated with carbon dioxide when a solid melting at 110° was isolated. This was insoluble in dilute acid, but was readily soluble in dilute alkali in cold and on warming this alkali solution with silver nitrate, a silver mirror was obtained. The mother-liquor left after separating the solid of m. p. 110°, on acidification afforded a gummy mass which also reduced silver nitrate solution. The filtrate showed the presence of primary aromatic amino compound on diazotisation.

Another part of the ammoniacal solution was diluted and cautiously treated with silver nitrate, when a white amorphous mass of silver salt was precipitated out. This was collected, washed free from silver nitrate, and was dried in a vacuum desiccator. The silver salt was not so susceptible to reduction in dry state. (Found: Ag, 27.8. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2S_2Ag$ requires Ag 27.5 per cent).

Treatment with Acid.—The compound dissolves in concentrated acids and is not precipitated on dilution. It (2 g.) was refluxed with 50 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid for 4 hours. A buff coloured solid (1.6 g.) was left behind. This was insoluble in alkali even on warming, insoluble in alcohol, pyridine, acetic acid, and chloroform. It charred at 302° .

The compound (2 g.) was heated at 40° for 3 hours with dilute hydrochloric acid (0.36%). About 1.98 g. of the unchanged substance was collected from the reaction mixture on filtration.

The substance (2 g.) was digested with 200 c.c. of dilute sulphuric acid (5%) in a distilling flask and the distillate was found to reduce an acid solution of dichromate. A hexamine solution on similar treatment evolved formaldehyde to reduce the dichromate in solution.

Reaction of Formalin with N-Methyl Derivative of Sulphathiazole.—Sulphathiazole exists in two forms; accordingly methylation of this sulphonamide derivative may give rise to two methyl derivatives (IV) and (V) (cf. Shepherd, *loc. cit.*). For the purpose of this investigation a silver salt of sulphathiazole was prepared by treating a solution of sodium salt of sulphathiazole with silver nitrate, and refluxed with 1.25 mol. of methyl iodide in anhydrous benzene for one hour. The reaction mixture was filtered off, and the benzene solution on evaporation afforded a solid melting indifferently at 140° - 210° , insoluble in dilute alkali, but soluble in dilute acid.

The filtrate (silver iodide mixture) was extracted with absolute alcohol, filtered and the alcohol evaporated off. The solid left behind was washed with a trace of dilute alcohol and ether, when it melted indifferently at 150° - 170° . It was also insoluble in dilute alkali but soluble in dilute acid. Both fractions were then mixed, triturated with dilute alkali to remove any sulphathiazole, filtered, washed with dilute alcohol and dried. The mixture melted indifferently at 160° - 170° and was completely soluble in dilute acid.

It was then dissolved in absolute alcohol by boiling, filtered hot, and the filtered solution was refluxed with formalin (molar amount) for 3 hours. It was then filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The mass obtained was triturated with dilute hydrochloric acid in which it was practically insoluble, and was crystallised from a large volume of boiling absolute alcohol in fine microscopic needles, m. p. 252° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.82. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 14.05 per cent).

This methylal derivative from sulphathiazole methyl compound is insoluble in dilute acid and in dilute alkali, but when heated with alkali in presence of silver nitrate solution it reduces the silver salt to silver mirror.

Reaction of Formalin with N⁴-Acetylsulphathiazole.—The acetylsulphathiazole was prepared by heating sulphathiazole (3 g.) with glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (2 c.c.). The solid of m. p. 272° is as usual soluble in alkali but is insolubl

in dilute acid. This was refluxed with formalin (1.25 mole) in glacial acetic acid solution for 3 hours. No solid separated out and from the acetic acid solution unchanged acetyl-sulphathiazole was recovered.

Reaction of Formic Acid with Sulphathiazole.—A mixture of sulphathiazole (2.9 g.) and formic acid (2 c.c. of 85% acid) was heated under reflux for 15 minutes. The reacted mixture was cooled, diluted with water and the solid left behind was filtered off. This was crystallised from alcohol (95%) in microscopic needles, m. p. 230°, sintering earlier. (Found : N, 14.8. $C_{10}H_8O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 14.8 per cent).

The N⁴-formylsulphathiazole (III) is insoluble in dilute acid and readily dissolves in alkali. The alkali solution on warming with a solution of silver nitrate formed a beautiful silver mirror. All these tend to show that sulphathiazole behaves in quite a different manner with formaldehyde and in the condensation product the mobility of N¹- as well as N⁴-hydrogen atom of the thiazole derivative has been inhibited by its reaction with formaldehyde with the formation of the compound of structure (I). As the parent compound may exist in two forms (IV) and (V), the resulting reaction product with formaldehyde may be methylene-N¹ : N¹-bis-(4-hydroxymethyl-2-sulphanilamido-thiazole) from (IV) and / or, methylene-3 : 3'-bis-(4-hydroxymethyl-2-sulphanilimido-2: 3-dihydrothiazole) from (V). Its non-solubility in common solvents points to the formation of the latter compound.

In conclusion the author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Mr. S. Banerjee, B.Sc. for carrying out some analyses in course of this investigation.